

OPEN LETTER

Open science and ethics in energy research

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Abstract

Energy research is evolving, with new methodologies, technologies, and challenges, while new communication tools allow for quick and cheap dissemination of information. In contrast, the publication of scientific research is still carried out by specialised journals, which serve a dual purpose as gatekeepers and disseminators but may delay the process of sharing the scientific knowledge. Data used in relevant research is often kept secret, and proprietary code and "black-box" models are barriers to replication. These practices raise ethical concerns as they may hinder the identification of research misconduct. Open science has gained momentum and aims to promote openness, reconnecting with traditional research principles. In this paper, we discuss the ethical and practical implications of the adoption of open science in energy research. Our goal is to give a broad understanding of the benefits and drawbacks of open science and present the ongoing discussions in the research community.

Keywords

open science, research ethics, energy research

This article is included in the [Horizon 2020](#) gateway.

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Open Peer Review

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Plain language summary

Open Science is becoming a key feature in promoting better research practices and reaching citizens and the non-expert public interested in the development of science. In a world where people are becoming more interconnected, academics can now reach a wider part of the population through open-access platforms that bridge the gap with experts. Despite the general acceptance of openness, there is a general lack of understanding of the implications for researchers and all the dimensions involved in fully reaching it (e.g., open methodology, open data).

In this paper, the authors describe what open science is, discuss how it is aligned with traditional research principles and present the benefits and drawbacks for scientists who adopt it. In particular, the authors focus on the domain of energy research, which, differently from other disciplines (e.g., medicine, mathematics), has been lagging in adopting Open Science practices. The paper intends to support research transparency and availability but also present and highlight the difficulties that researchers might encounter before, during and after making their research open to the public.

I. Introduction

Research has been affected throughout history by the scientific ethos of the moment. For example, in medieval times, the encouraging attitude was to withhold knowledge from the “vulgar multitude”, enticing arcane and occult information to a selected group¹. While the protection of trade secrets and intellectual rights can be beneficial for entrepreneurship, this behaviour can be detrimental to society if it stands in the way of public access to scientific knowledge, especially regarding matters of common consequence.

Modern societies have gradually incorporated science as a fundamental feature that defines the productive forces, power structures, social classes, or political actions, among other societal features². Therefore, making science accessible could bring considerable benefits to society and the research community, such as financial savings, increase development of scientific education and dissemination in the Global South, or promotion of sustainable practices³.

In recent years, many disciplines have been prone to adopt open science as common practice, such as astronomy, genomics, or oceanography⁴. This shift is not so prevalent in energy research, as it is still common to use black-box models and private data that hinder discussion and verification⁵. Instead, ethical discussion in the energy field has focused on essential questions, such as [climate change](#) or [energy justice](#). Considering the influence of the field of research in politics and society and vice versa⁶, we argue that openness and transparency should be also included as a significant topic for discussion in energy research.

This essay aims to analyse the adoption of open science and evaluate its integration in the energy research domain.

In [Section 2](#) we provide a brief overview of the definition of open science and discuss its benefits and drawbacks. Thereafter, we focus on elaborating more in detail on the current application and implications of open science in energy research. Finally, we discuss and conclude with the key elements and lessons learned.

II. Open science: definition

A widely used definition for open science comes from Michael Nielsen⁷ and states: “open science is the idea that scientific knowledge of all kinds should be openly shared as early as is practical in the discovery process”. A similar and shorter definition can be found in the “[Guide to Open Science](#)”, where open science is “the idea that scientific research should be openly and immediately shared”. Hence, it promotes universal participation and encourages [data distribution in standardized formats](#). This concept of openness in science can be linked to the traditional ethic values stipulated by Robert Merton⁸ which have been used as fundamental ideals of scientific practice⁹. The four values are: *communism* (collaboration and cooperation), *universalism* (avoid secrecy and ensure accessibility), *disinterestedness* (relegate individual motives) and *organised skepticism* (to extend previous findings).

Open science goes beyond open data or open access as it provides accessibility to a wider variety of resources such as analysis and methods⁴. The [six principles of open science](#) are open methodology, open source, open data, open access, open peer review and open educational resources.

In open science, the praxis of open methodology is to increase transparency and homogeneity in the documentation of methodological approaches taken in scientific research. This practice is one of the least divisive principles of open science, as good methodological practices have been a top requisite for high-quality scientific publications. The possibility of revising methodological approaches promotes discussions and incentives for the elaboration of new research.

Another principle of open science is the promotion of open source. It is usually framed around the concept of technology or science developed through collective effort and community guidance. Pursuing open source is a rupture from the closed-gates form of development present in some technological platforms. Researchers voluntarily choose to use and develop scientific tools that are available without barriers, allowing for more reproducible experiments and the availability of software.

Adopting open data requires that scientific databases become publicly available. Other researchers are, in this way, incentivised to conduct alternative experiments with the available data. Open data can boost collaboration and promote comparable studies among researchers in line with Mertonian values. Another benefit of openness is that it may reduce the time and resources deployed to gather information. Some

studies also examine the potential use of open data as a qualitative metric of scientific success^{4,10}.

The praxis of open access aims to use the possibilities provided by new communication technologies to disseminate scientific knowledge freely and without discrimination. In some cases, researchers are not required to pay to publish, and everyone can benefit from the electronic distribution of scientific literature.

Quality assurance has been a service provided by the scientific publishing industry. It usually consists of editors making a quick and specific filter and specialists in the subject reviewing papers in more depth. This revision process is often anonymous and voluntary to promote objectivity. Open peer review proposes a similar evaluation process which is conducted in an open and sometimes decentralized environment. This field, however, is still under development, keeping up with the adoption of open access.

Finally, the principle of open educational resources promotes the elaboration of free and accessible materials that can enhance the education of researchers, students, or any person interested in learning science.

III. Open science for prevention of bad research practices

In addition to the benefits associated with open dissemination, academia aims to prevent practices that are not considered appropriate when pursuing research through the adoption of open science. We distinguish two types of bad research practices: scientific misconduct and questionable research practices. The former includes behaviours that can be sanctioned according to research ethics regulations, whereas the latter, despite being considered not desirable, is not associated with penalisation procedures. The U.S. Office of Research Integrity [defines scientific misconduct](#) as:

“[...] fabrication, falsification, or plagiarism in proposing, performing, or reviewing research, or in reporting research results.

(a) Fabrication is making up data or results and recording or reporting them.

(b) Falsification is manipulating research materials, equipment, or processes, or changing or omitting data or results such that the research is not accurately represented in the research record.

(c) Plagiarism is the appropriation of another person's ideas, processes, results, or words without giving appropriate credit.

(d) Research misconduct does not include honest error or differences of opinion”

Behaviours that belong to the category of questionable research practices are, for example, selecting specific references to back up hypotheses, not reporting unexpected results, or not stating all the investigation conditions. Given the greater likelihood of researchers committing these infringements, some scientists claim that these are the real source of harm to research integrity^{11,12}.

Besides the possibility of individual punishment for scientific misconducts, all these bad research practices have long-term consequences for the whole scientific community such as mistrust in science, loss of social justification, and the generation of misleading insights that risk the role of science in society.

Open science can prevent these undesirable research practices by inducing the reproducibility of research. Allowing other researchers to reuse the data and methods (e.g., code) used for the publications enhances the chance to detect bad research practices.

A. Barriers and shortcomings of open science

The three main drawbacks of sharing scientific resources are, according to Feigenbaum and Levy¹³, additional effort, interference with future work, and verification as a double-edged sword.

It is not unusual to find researchers who consider that preparing resources for external interested parties is time-consuming or negative for their future research. In an experiment two hundred researchers were asked to share the supplementary material as promised in their articles¹⁴. Only 40% shared the requested material, and most of the rejections claimed that it was not worth their time. A similar study received similar refusals arguing that sharing their resources could interfere with their ongoing projects¹⁵.

Enhancing verification and reviewing processes could be considered a double-edged sword because it could improve the quality of research¹⁶, but also ease the identification of non-voluntary questionable practices that may harm researchers' recognition. The possibility of being involved in professional controversies may increase fear toward the adoption of open science¹³, especially in a competitive environment. In this regard, competition in the research community has proven to limit collaboration and sharing practices¹⁷ or has been even considered as the root of bad research practices¹⁸. While professional interests [might be seen](#) as a questionable reason for not engaging in open science, other reasons can be aligned with ethical concerns such as patient/customer privacy, confidentiality, and copyright issues.

Another barrier to implementing open access is related to the publishing industry revenue structure¹⁹. Mainstream journals perform several functions in the current research

publication environment, such as archival research information for posterity, registration of scientific discovery to establish precedence, dissemination of scientific knowledge, and certification asserting rigour and significance of contributions²⁰. Decoupling those functions into different services could promote a different stream of revenue for journals, for instance, authors could pay to register a discovery, or pay for a review from an editor, and in exchange, the journal could allow open access and archival function with no charge to the readers.

Understanding open science as a synonym of quality could lead to negative outcomes as it does not warrant appropriate methodologies or well-oriented questions. Open science could lead to “flaw studies or junk science” if researchers stick their studies to available resources instead of pursuing valuable investigation paths¹⁰.

Open science also lacks maturity in the tools that warrant a minimal level of quality, which is attained through the editorial process in most journals nowadays. Some open access repositories, especially preprint servers, do not perform any kind of pre-publication analysis. Although post-publication criticism is possible, it is not always visible or arranged in a relevant manner. A large number of publications without any form of analysis could paradoxically foster more fabrication, falsification, and plagiarism. The benefit of transparency is then lost under unrestricted publication.

Quality mechanisms for open science are being developed, and open peer review is already under development. Other means, such as citations, are already decentralized and can be maintained. Some studies^{7,21} identify the quality metrics currently used, e.g., citations and impact factor, as tools that do not promote the correct incentive. Because of this, alternative metrics have been suggested, and they are called collectively “altmetrics”^{22,23}, some of which are already being adopted by the traditional publishing industry.

IV. Open science and energy research

A characteristic of energy research is its repercussions on political decision-making and, consequently, on society and the environment²⁴. Not following the scientific ethos could increase mistrust, not only in science but also in governments and legal administrations. Transparency and accessible energy science are as important as ever with global concerns such as climate change, supply crisis caused by war or the economic recovery after the coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic.

Open science has multiple positive outcomes (e.g., collaboration, identifying bad practices). However, Pfenninger *et al.*²⁵ identify four prevalent outcomes that fit with energy

research practices. These are: (1) easing the identification of errors in models and assumptions, (2) improvements in the researchers’ productivity, (3) incorporating more scientific arguments in societal debates, and (4) the promotion of better cooperation between policy and research.

Another positive aspect of open science is its ability to homogenise data and metadata. Ensuring a common understanding is particularly important in fields that are associated with multiple disciplines as it is the case of energy research (e.g., operations research, macroeconomics, power system engineering, energy policy). With such a variety of understandings about the same topic, one usually encounters different terminologies, assumptions, or modelling techniques⁴. This heterogeneity may hinder the exchange of insights between disciplines, resulting in studies with a narrow scope and disciplinarily myopia²⁶, a problem that could be solved by enhancing collaboration.

In energy domains where innovation is patentable, private capital might invest in research and development for commercial purposes. In this setting, it is expected that the societal cost of not having access to information is not as significant as the cost of burdening the risk of failure. This applies particularly well to research oriented towards developing business models and new technologies (e.g., new battery materials, designs of wind turbines, software for operating energy management systems). Other domains related to energy science rely mostly on public funding, such as energy policies or environmental studies. It is a matter of debate whether the knowledge developed with public funding should have restricted publications and data and use software that charge a fee to grant access, thus being less reproducible.

A recent paper by Hart *et al.*²¹ lists many benefits of open science to engineering, but many of the impacts can be extrapolated for research in similar fields, such as energy. The authors point out that filing for patents is often more costly than whatever revenue is obtained, as it is a time-consuming process which take research away from its focus, and it is not necessary for obtaining private funding. The authors conclude with an analogy that will be familiar to many using optimisation tools: open science has a similar effect on research as a less constrained model, usually improving the objective function.

Friesike *et al.*⁷ make a parallel between open science and open innovation, identifying many convergent aspects and suggesting that the adoption of open science might describe an inevitable paradigm shift. They present several trends that shape the future of open science, which are a higher acceptance of open access, the emergence of open reviewing and new quality measurements, new distribution models for collective knowledge creation, more

interdisciplinary research, outsourcing of research from within small and medium companies and intellectual property trading. Those trends can be identified within the energy field, especially regarding research collaboration between companies and universities.

To promote open science in the field of energy research, Howells *et al.*²⁷ propose a guideline on how energy modellers could present their research to experts and non-experts. Key recommendations are compactness to ease the learning process, deployment of free-access programming languages (e.g., Python), explanations in plain English, and presentation of all data input. Similarly, Hilpert *et al.*²⁸ describe an approach for open modelling energy systems to tackle more complex and wide-ranging problems, for which collaboration can provide the best answer.

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in embracing open science in the energy field, particularly from academia and political organisations. The [OpenMod](#) (Open Energy Modelling) initiative arose in 2012 due to the concerns around the deployment of “black-boxes” in the energy domain that could undermine the reputation of the field and result in inefficiencies for the researchers. This international initiative has united open access resources ranging from data, models, and references to other open science initiatives related to the energy field.

Another example of an effort to incorporate open science in energy research is the Horizon2020 framework. One of its goals focuses on bringing science closer to society by [promoting the three O’s as strategies](#): open innovation, open science, and open to the world. The EU Open Data Portal, following the ethical outlines, contains free-access datasets of diverse research domains. The [number of entries](#) for the energy category is remarkably low compared to other research fields (1,094 datasets in “Energy” compared to 4,033 in “Population and Society”, 3,093 in “Environment” or 2,952 in “Science and Technology”). These numbers can have their roots in the number of projects funded, but they might also reveal that there are substantial barriers to open science in the energy domain. When analysing the percentage of open access publications, we find that energy research falls behind domains such as medicine or mathematics (see [Figure 1](#)).

Many energy firms and research institutes largely rely on the income provided by owning energy data and models (e.g., utilities, consultants). Due to the crucial role of models in their economic performance, open science faces a strong barrier within these organisations.

New communication technologies can pose a positive and necessary change in the energy landscape. Recently, new movements promoted the unrestricted use of collaborative

tools (e.g., OpenMod, European Data Portal, OpenEI), bridging the current energy research environment and the Mertonian ideals based on open science. Also, high-profile scientific journals already offer some degree of open-access space for publication (e.g., *Energies*, *Energy and Policy Research*).

Not pursuing openness when presenting energy models could lead to fewer repercussions in the scientific field. This is a problem that leads to more discrepancies between decision-makers and energy researchers²⁶. Lawmakers tend to criticise the possibility of energy models being the product of energy lobbies. Therefore, transparency is required when presenting assumptions, inaccuracies, and limitations of models to ease the understanding of insights from science and increase credibility. Openness can be considered a vital practice for energy research as it has considerable implications in its applicability.

Moreover, these tools are usually developed over the years. Thus, their complexity may be an obstacle to new users. As a result, an interagency review is deployed, for example, in the U.S. to check the different results and evaluate the models’ reliability²⁶. In this way, decision-makers do not need to deeply comprehend the models to understand their insights, assumptions, and limitations. Although openness at this level overcomes the accessibility barrier for policymakers, it does not guarantee appropriate disclosure of the results to the rest of the population, resulting in a society lacking the knowledge to understand the reasons for energy policies.

As in other scientific fields, energy research is difficult to comprehend without some education. Therefore, energy-related knowledge should be taught and disseminated through open educational resources that reach a higher share of society. Universal access to education is becoming more common in the energy domain with conferences and workshops open to the general public (A.C.M. e-Energy, D-A-CH+ Conference on Energy Informatics or Future Technologies Conference) and Open Courseware uploaded on platforms like YouTube or Coursera.

V. Discussion

Open science is a multidimensional practice that involves more than sharing of data and can be directly associated with traditional research ethics. It can help to lower the likelihood of research misconducts, disseminate knowledge worldwide, ease collaboration among researchers, industries, and decision-makers, and could enhance the quality of research, either by reducing rework or by redirecting new research.

Interestingly, the practices within open science enhance each other. For example, open education is an enabler of the use of open access resources, as it gives the reader more

Figure 1. Development of the percentage of open access over all publications for different research fields. Data retrieved from Scopus.

knowledge to interpret results and methodology innovation. A second example is how the effectiveness of open peer-review can be enhanced by open data and open methodology.

Despite its benefits, the adoption of open science is not enough to avoid scientific ailments. Active participation from the readers is required to ensure discussion and validation of the published resources, as allowing for universal access is, in itself, not a measure of quality. The same applies to scientific misconduct because shared resources need to be analysed to identify flaws. Open science requires engagement from researchers or content creators as well as from the recipients of the resource.

Nevertheless, ensuring engagement seems to be a major obstacle to the adoption of open science. Researchers may look at it as a time-consuming activity or perceive it as having a negative impact by interfering with the prospect of future projects. The negative view towards open science is enhanced within highly competitive sectors, in which researchers' time and proprietary resources are key to getting founded and gaining prestige. Another major obstacle is related to the structural changes required on the publishing side, including new quality metrics and open peer-review.

As researchers in the energy field, we see how it can benefit from open science principles. Based on our study, the most prevalent benefits are improving collaboration and linkage between multiple disciplines within the field, sharing standardized data and methodologies, and enhancing communication with decision-makers by allowing more access to information and education.

It is visible that the adoption of open science in energy research is progressing, as it is reflected in open access being a requisite for funding, in the increase and

development of projects fully oriented to open science (e.g., [Open Entrance](#)), and in the prevalence of workshops and conferences with public access.

Despite the progress toward openness, research in the energy field faces significant barriers. Energy-related industries are more likely to fund private projects or limit the publication of data and findings, which could threaten their prestige, credibility, or market position. Moreover, data privacy (e.g., end user consumption patterns) and energy security concerns are legitimate barriers that might be slowing down the integration of open science. Those limitations and shortcomings do not constitute reasons not to adopt open science but cautionary measures to be considered when choosing it.

We agree that open science is undergoing a paradigm shift, one that should be undertaken while considering its benefits and drawbacks. The purpose of this paper is to update this discussion and keep it at the forefront, assuring that better collaboration and research practices will help us all in the energy field to tackle the great challenges ahead.

Ethics and consent

Ethical approval and consent were not required.

Data availability

No data are associated with this article.

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Gesche Huebner

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I overall much enjoyed reading this open letter; open science and ethics in energy research important and overlooked aspect. The authors describe what open science is and discuss its benefits and drawbacks. They then focus on the energy research sector and show how it lags behind other disciplines

I have four points I suggest the authors to engage with:

1. In the discussion of open data, I would expect to see the FAIR principles mentioned, i.e. Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability, see e.g. here: <https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201618>. Also, adding some citations around the benefits of open data would be appropriate (e.g. <https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0230416> but there are others).
2. As a reviewer, it is always awkward pointing to your own publications but myself and colleagues have published previously around openness and transparency in energy research, reflecting on many of the difficulties mentioned by the authors of this paper, such as the heterogeneity of energy research and the quick changes in the energy landscape. We would encourage the authors to engage with our publications, in particular this peer-reviewed journal article: Huebner, GM; Fell, MJ; Watson, NE; (2021) Improving energy research practices: guidance for transparency, reproducibility and quality. **Buildings & Cities**, 2 (1) pp. 1-20. [10.5334/bc.67](https://doi.org/10.5334/bc.67).
3. The discussion of the publishing industry revenue structure could be given more depth. There have been quite a lot of changes, see e.g. here for a discussion on Plan S (<https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-021-00883-6>); there are different levels of open access (Gold vs. Green) etc. Also, I cannot quite follow the argument how creating different streams of revenue would aid open access. Many journals already are open access or have an open access option (even subscription journals). Is the idea here to replace the subscription model with an open access model through payment for individual services

instead of a university subscribing to a journal / publisher? Could there be unintended consequences especially for more junior scholars / those not holding large grants?

4. About preprints being potentially problematic because of the lack of oversight, this is a fair point – but they bring many benefits (e.g. earlier and wider access to scientific findings; possibility to include not yet published work in grant applications by linking to a preprint) and it might be an option to simply shape a mindset that preprints come with a ‘health warning’. E.g. preprint servers could overlay all preprints with a clear message saying “not peer-reviewed, no assessment of validity and reliability done” and the onus would be on the reader to interpret them as preliminary.

Finally, the paper nicely lays out how energy research is heterogeneous but then it does focus in particular on energy systems modelling and its open modelling initiative. Whilst this is an incredibly important topic, energy research is much broader and some more nuance around this might be nice to add.

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Is the rationale for the Open Letter provided in sufficient detail? (Please consider whether existing challenges in the field are outlined clearly and whether the purpose of the letter is explained)

Yes

Does the article adequately reference differing views and opinions?

Yes

Are all factual statements correct, and are statements and arguments made adequately supported by citations?

Partly

Is the Open Letter written in accessible language? (Please consider whether all subject-specific terms, concepts and abbreviations are explained)

Yes

Where applicable, are recommendations and next steps explained clearly for others to follow? (Please consider whether others in the research community would be able to implement guidelines or recommendations and/or constructively engage in the debate)

Not applicable

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: energy research; open science

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 14 Jan 2025

Raquel Alonso Pedrero

We are very grateful for your comments and positive feedback. Please find below your feedback, followed by our replies.

Reviewer Comments:

General Comments:

I overall much enjoyed reading this open letter; open science and ethics in energy research important and overlooked aspect. The authors describe what open science is and discuss its benefits and drawbacks. They then focus on the energy research sector and show how it lags behind other disciplines

I have four points I suggest the authors to engage with:

Author Response:

We are very glad to know that you found the topic interesting and meaningful. Also, we are grateful to get your feedback as it improved the quality of the new manuscript. Each comment is addressed below.

Comment 1:

In the discussion of open data, I would expect to see the FAIR principles mentioned, i.e. Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability, see e.g. here:

<https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201618>. Also, adding some citations around the benefits of open data would be appropriate (e.g.

<https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0230416> but there are others).

Author Response:

Thank you. We agree that the FAIR principles are essential when discussing open science. We revised Section II to reflect this. In the subsection "C. Applying open science", focused on the integration of open science in research, we introduce the FAIR principles. Moreover, the new description of the key principles of open science now includes citations as one of the benefits of open data, including the citation to the suggested article.

Comment 2:

As a reviewer, it is always awkward pointing to your own publications but myself and colleagues have published previously around openness and transparency in energy

research, reflecting on many of the difficulties mentioned by the authors of this paper, such as the heterogeneity of energy research and the quick changes in the energy landscape. We would encourage the authors to engage with our publications, in particular this peer-reviewed journal article: Huebner, GM; Fell, MJ; Watson, NE; (2021) Improving energy research practices: guidance for transparency, reproducibility and quality. *Buildings & Cities*, 2 (1) pp. 1-20. [10.5334/bc.67](https://doi.org/10.5334/bc.67).

Author Response:

Thank you for recommending your paper, it was a definitely a publication that we needed to read. We enjoyed the discussion, and the approach proposed in the paper, especially in how it tackles different stages in the research process. In our understanding, each tool adheres with the principles of open science. As such, we included the following paragraph in section IV:

“Huebner et al. (2021) introduced the TREQ approach, a set of four tools to reduce questionable research practices. These tools include preregistering analysis plans, reporting guidelines, sharing preprints of papers, and making data and code open. Each tool promotes openness at different stages of the research process and allows researchers to prevent issues like data manipulation, insufficient details of methods, and lack of reproducibility, among others.”

Comment 3:

The discussion of the publishing industry revenue structure could be given more depth. There have been quite a lot of changes, see e.g. here for a discussion on Plan S (<https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-021-00883-6>); there are different levels of open access (Gold vs. Green) etc. Also, I cannot quite follow the argument how creating different streams of revenue would aid open access. Many journals already are open access or have an open access option (even subscription journals). Is the idea here to replace the subscription model with an open access model through payment for individual services instead of a university subscribing to a journal / publisher? Could there be unintended consequences especially for more junior scholars / those not holding large grants?

Author Response:

We thank the reviewer for this comment. A similar point was brought forward by another reviewer. The analysis of the decoupling argument in the first version of the paper was misdirected. The paragraph has been re-written to better convey the original message put up by the referenced papers. We hope to have made the motivation and the argument clearer.

Comment 4:

About preprints being potentially problematic because of the lack of oversight, this is a fair point – but they bring many benefits (e.g. earlier and wider access to scientific findings; possibility to include not yet published work in grant applications by linking to a preprint) and it might be an option to simply shape a mindset that preprints come with a ‘health warning’. E.g. preprint servers could overlay all preprints with a clear message saying “not peer-reviewed, no assessment of validity and reliability done” and the onus would be on the reader to interpret them as preliminary.

Author Response:

We agree with the reviewer and incorporated part of the text of the comment in the

updated version of the paper.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Report 19 July 2023

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.16970.r31993>

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Sacha Hodencq

University Grenoble Alpes, Saint-Martin-d'Hères, Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes, France

The Open letter “Open science and ethics in energy research” introduces the context of open science in current research practices. After defining open science itself, it discusses its interests and limits, in particular in the energy research field.

The letter provides an overview of current work and discussion on the topic, with a good number of references. It underlines the interests of open practices in the energy field, and the necessary distinction between openness and quality. It includes interesting conclusions on the need for open science despite its limitations, and the paradigm shift it necessitates.

I believe the letter could still be improved. Generally speaking, by being more explicit about whether the subject is open science or its sub-components (in particular differentiating open science from open access) in order to avoid confusion, based on more recent references; and by clarifying the ethics mentioned in the title.

This review generally follows the sequence of the letter.

In the **section II.**, The definition of open science from Michael Nielsen that is provided seems indeed well established. A recent and comprehensive reference that could also be included is the UNESCO recommendation on Open Science ¹ that explicitly encompasses various movements and practices in the Open Science definition, contrary to the following definition from the Guide to Open Science that focuses on Open access and, to a certain extent, on open data and open source software, or to the definition from Kraker et al. 2011 ² (by the way, if this reference is kept, please quote the Kraker et al. 2011 article rather than the openscienceasap website that is not available in English). I believe including the UNESCO open science definition as well as recommendations could enrich the letter contents. This would for instance enable to include open hardware in addition to open source software in the 4th paragraph of the section II., and give referenced definition of those concepts. The explicit mention of the 4 Mertonian values does not seem essential here, as their link with open science is not developed in the letter nor in the references from what I read (the link with universalism and communism seems intuitive, it is less the case with the other two), and these Mertonian values are not reused later in the letter. I would also point out that Mertonian values have been criticised as for their idealised view of the way research

is carried out, but I understand this is out of the scope of this letter ⁴. An additional interesting reference in my view in the Open Science Training Handbook from the European program FOSTER ³, that was first released in 2018, and includes good definitions and details, for instance to support the open access and quality insurance paragraphs in section II.

In **section III.**, the first paragraphs explore ethics as the prevention from bad research practices. Energy systems are complex socio-technical systems with great environmental and social impacts, as mentioned in the introduction. So the energy research field call for both research ethics and integrity. In my view, the article focuses on integrity rather than ethics generally speaking. So my advice would be whether to expand on ethical aspects of energy research; or more realistically, to define more clearly the scope of ethical exploration from the title and introduction, as otherwise, one could expect deeper ethical development of open science in energy research. In the 4th paragraph of section III.A., I do not fully understand why the functions decoupling is conditional: from my understanding, it sounds like the Golden open access model ⁴ that more and more journals are using (not the majority though). Moreover, I feel it should be made more explicit where the subject is open science generally speaking (as it is well done in the paragraph right before section III.A), and when the subject is open access. For instance in the last two paragraphs of section III., I feel that what is discussed is open access scientific publication, and not open science generally speaking.

In the **section IV.**, the 3rd paragraph about terminologies could mention the Open Energy Ontology project ⁵, or generally speaking articles exploring the questions of ontology in energy modelling such as the one from Pritoni et al. ⁶. The 4th paragraph of this section could mention the coalitionS that has achieved big steps in the open access publication of result from research funded by public grants ⁷. The 5th paragraph could mention papers that specifically explored the benefits of open science in energy research, such as the ones from Morrison, Pfenninger et al., Bazilian et al. or. ^{8,9,10}. For what it's worth, I tried to synthetise these interests in ¹¹. Then the checklist from Cao et al. ¹² could be mentioned in the 7th paragraph regarding the guidelines. In the 9th paragraph, is the number of projects funded in the energy field known? If so, please share it here. In the 10th paragraph, a very representative example of this is the International Energy Agency, see Ritchie and Roser ¹³. The last paragraph of this section could also mention the teaching materials from OSeMOSYS ¹⁴.

In the **Discussion**, paragraph 4: Morrison ⁸ argues that the (time) resources consumed for openness is often outweighed by the external contributions, this might be worth mentioning it.

Regarding the form of the letter:

- end of third paragraph of the *Introduction section*: “also” should be put before “be”
- section II., 5th paragraph: rather than “other researchers are [...] incentivised”, I would say “other researchers are [...] offered the possibility”, as, in my view, they are not incentivised.
- There is a section III.A but no section III.B
- Section IV., 2nd paragraph: I would say “in particular” rather than “however”, as to me, Pfenninger et al. go in the same direction as what was discussed beforehand.
- Section IV., 7th paragraph: As mentioned on the Python website ¹⁵, I would present the

programming languages as an “open-source” rather than “free access”.

- Section IV., 8th paragraph: I would talk about “black-box models” rather than “black-boxes”, and then talk about open resources rather than “open access resources”. A good reference here is Pfenninger et al. ⁸.
- Section IV, in terms of flow of thoughts, I feel the paragraphs 11 and 12 could be brought closer to the 5th, as they seem to develop the interests of open science in the energy field.

Disclaimer: this review represents my current view on the topic, and can obviously be constructively criticised as well.

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15. [Reference Source](#)

Is the rationale for the Open Letter provided in sufficient detail? (Please consider whether existing challenges in the field are outlined clearly and whether the purpose of the letter is explained)

Partly

Does the article adequately reference differing views and opinions?

Partly

Are all factual statements correct, and are statements and arguments made adequately supported by citations?

Partly

Is the Open Letter written in accessible language? (Please consider whether all subject-specific terms, concepts and abbreviations are explained)

Yes

Where applicable, are recommendations and next steps explained clearly for others to follow? (Please consider whether others in the research community would be able to implement guidelines or recommendations and/or constructively engage in the debate)

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: My research mainly focuses on open science and energy modelling. I am a member of the French committee for Open Science.

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 14 Jan 2025

Raquel Alonso Pedrero

Thanks for your constructive feedback and interesting question raised. General Comments: The Open letter "Open science and ethics in energy research" introduces the context of open science in current research practices. After defining open science itself, it discusses its interests and limits, in particular in the energy research field. The letter provides an overview of current work and discussion on the topic, with a good number of references. It underlines the interests of open practices in the energy field, and the necessary distinction between openness and quality. It includes interesting conclusions on the need for open science despite its limitations, and the paradigm shift it necessitates. I believe the letter could still be improved. Generally speaking, by being more explicit about whether the subject is open science or its sub-components (in particular differentiating open science from open access) in order to avoid confusion, based on more recent references; and by clarifying the ethics mentioned in the title.

Response:

Thank you for your comments and your feedback. We have addressed all the concerns in the comments below. In the new manuscript, we aimed to be more explicit and clear about the ideas we wanted to convey and be more cautious with the wording. We remove the ethics mentioned in the title and focus on presenting open science and its benefits, barriers and integration in energy research.

Comment 1:

In the section II., The definition of open science from Michael Nielsen that is provided seems indeed well established. A recent and comprehensive reference that could also be included is the UNESCO recommendation on Open Science 1 that explicitly encompasses various movements and practices in the Open Science definition, contrary to the following definition from the Guide to Open Science that focuses on Open access and, to a certain extent, on open data and open source software, or to the definition from Kraker et al. 2011 2 (by the way, if this reference is kept, please quote the Kraker et al. 2011 article rather than the openscienceasap website that is not available in English). I believe including the UNESCO open science definition as well as recommendations could enrich the letter contents. This would for instance enable to include open hardware in addition to open source software in the 4th paragraph of the section II., and give referenced definition of those concepts.

Response:

We really appreciate the suggestions and insights provided. In the new manuscript, we kept Michael Nielsen's and the Guide to Open Science's definitions, given their well-established status. Then, we clarified that open science integrates more principles based on Kraker et al. (2011) and UNESCO (2021). Also, following the UNESCO guidelines and your suggestion, we added open hardware as one of the key principles.

Comment 2:

The explicit mention of the 4 Mertonian values does not seem essential here, as their link with open science is not developed in the letter nor in the references from what I read (the link with universalism and communism seems intuitive, it is less the case with the other two), and these Mertonian values are not reused later in the letter. I would also point out that Mertonian values have been criticised as for their idealised view of the way research is carried out, but I understand this is out of the scope of this letter 4.

Response:

We share your concern that linking the Mertonian values with open science in the paper is separate from the rest of the paper's content. Given that the topic is open science in energy research, we eliminated the word ethics from the title and removed the text referring to the Mertonian values from Section I. Still, we kept this intuitive connection with universalism and communism in the introduction as a way of emphasizing the alignment between open science and the ethos in science and as a starting point for the paper.

Comment 3:

An additional interesting reference in my view in the Open Science Training Handbook from the European program FOSTER 3, that was first released in 2018, and includes good definitions and details, for instance to support the open access and quality insurance paragraphs in section II.

Response:

This was a valuable comment. In the new manuscript, the structure in section I is divided into three new subsections, one addressing its integration (C. Applying open science). In this section, the Open Science Training Handbook, in combination with the FAIR principles, are presented as guidelines or frameworks to support the adoption and practice of open science.

Comment 4:

In section III., the first paragraphs explore ethics as the prevention from bad research practices. Energy systems are complex socio-technical systems with great environmental and social impacts, as mentioned in the introduction. So the energy research field call for both research ethics and integrity. In my view, the article focuses on integrity rather than ethics generally speaking. So my advice would be whether to expand on ethical aspects of energy research; or more realistically, to define more clearly the scope of ethical exploration from the title and introduction, as otherwise, one could expect deeper ethical development of open science in energy research.

Response:

We appreciate the reviewer highlighting the distinction between ethics and integrity in research. The old manuscript failed to address clear ethical aspects such as environmental impact, social justice, public engagement, etc. Instead, it was more focused on the conduct and process of research. One can argue that open science tackles the ethical concern of transparency, but the title and the introduction still led to the expectation of a more detailed discussion on ethics. The new manuscript was rewritten focusing on research integrity through open science and its application in energy research. As such, the title was modified by removing the term ethics.

Comment 5:

In the 4th paragraph of section III.A., I do not fully understand why the functions decoupling is conditional: from my understanding, it sounds like the Golden open access model 4 that more and more journals are using (not the majority though). Moreover, I feel it should be made more explicit where the subject is open science generally speaking (as it is well done in the paragraph right before section III.A), and when the subject is open access. For instance in the last two paragraphs of section III., I feel that what is discussed is open access scientific publication, and not open science generally speaking.

Response: We thank the reviewer for this comment. A similar point was brought forward by another reviewer. The analysis of the decoupling argument in the first version of the paper was misdirected. The paragraph has been re-written to better convey the original message put up by the referenced papers. We hope to have made the motivation and the argument clearer.

Comment 6:

In the section IV., the 3rd paragraph about terminologies could mention the Open Energy Ontology project 5, or generally speaking articles exploring the questions of ontology in energy modelling such as the one from Pritoni et al. 6.

Response: We thank the reviewer for this comment. Both references were included in section IV, subsection A.

Comment 7:

The 4th paragraph of this section (section IV) could mention the coalitionS that has achieved big steps in the open access publication of result from research funded by public grants 7.

Response: Thank you for the suggestion. CoalitionS and Plan S focus on open access across all scientific disciplines, not just energy research. Therefore, we believe it is appropriate to mention them in Section II C. Applying open science, where we discuss the application of open science in a wider context.

Comment 8:

The 5th paragraph could mention papers that specifically explored the benefits of open science in energy research, such as the ones from Morrison, Pfenninger et al., Bazilian et al. or 8,9,10. For what it's worth, I tried to synthesise these interests in 11.

Response: We thank the reviewer for those most important sources. We make use of those references mostly in section IV.

Comment 9:

- Then the checklist from Cao et al. 12 could be mentioned in the 7th paragraph regarding the guidelines.
- In the 9th paragraph, is the number of projects funded in the energy field known? If so, please share it here.
- In the 10th paragraph, a very representative example of this is the International Energy Agency, see Ritchie and Roser 13.
- The last paragraph of this section could also mention the teaching materials from OSeMOSYS 14.
- In the Discussion, paragraph 4: Morrison 8 argues that the (time) resources consumed for openness is often outweighed by the external contributions, this might be worth mentioning it.

Response:

- We thank the reviewer for the reference suggestion, In the new version of the manuscript, the work of Cao et al. (2016) was mentioned alongside other relevant papers in section IV, subsection C.
- Based on this and other comments, we believe that the section comparing the adherence to open science between disciplines was not sufficiently detailed and was out of the scope of the paper. Thus, it is no longer part of the paper.
- We included this reference in section IV, subsection IV, citing alongside renewables.ninja.
- The teaching materials from OSeMOSYS and the link to its webpage are included in the new manuscript (last paragraph Section IV).
- Thanks for raising this point, we found it a valid limitation to open source. We included it in Section IV B.

Comment 10: Regarding the form of the letter:

- End of third paragraph of the Introduction section: "also" should be put before "be".
- Section II., 5th paragraph: rather than "other researchers are [...] incentivised", I would say "other researchers are [...] offered the possibility", as, in my view, they are not incentivised.
- There is a section III.A but no section III.B
- Section IV., 2nd paragraph: I would say "in particular" rather than "however", as to me, Pfenninger et al. go in the same direction as what was discussed beforehand.
- Section IV., 7th paragraph: As mentioned on the Python website 15, I would present the programming languages as an "open-source" rather than "free access".
- Section IV., 8th paragraph: I would talk about "black-box models" rather than "black-boxes", and then talk about open resources rather than "open access resources". A good reference here is Pfenninger et al. 8.
- Section IV, in terms of flow of thoughts, I feel the paragraphs 11 and 12 could be

brought closer to the 5th, as they seem to develop the interests of open science in the energy field.

Disclaimer: this review represents my current view on the topic, and can obviously be constructively criticised as well.

Response:

- The referred sentence is no longer part of the new manuscript.
- We agree “incentivised” was not correct in this context. Nonetheless, we took out this sentence from the manuscript.
- The new manuscript divides Section III into five subsections, solving the issue mentioned.
- True. The sentence was rewritten as:
“Transparency on models and assumptions not only addresses mistrust from society but also benefits the development of the research domain by enhancing feedback and enabling the correction of errors. Pfenninger et al. [31] identify other three beneficial outcomes of adhering to open science in energy research”
- Thanks for the suggestion, the word was modified to keep consistency throughout the text.
- We now refer only to “black-box models” and “open resources”.
- Thanks for the suggestion. We felt that Section IV needed to be reorganized based on specific ideas. We hope the new version presents a more ordered flow of thought.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Report 19 July 2023

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.16970.r31997>

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Rosie Robison

Anglia Ruskin University, Chelmsford, England, UK

Ami Crowther

Anglia Ruskin University, Chelmsford, England, UK

This is an interesting paper which draws out and reflects open science within the context of energy research. Within the paper, focus is placed upon the ethical dimensions of open science, although we feel this key message should be made more prominent in the paper’s narrative before approval.

General Points

Overall, the paper is well written but greater effort could be made to ensure the overarching narrative is clear and the central points are emphasised. The use of more 'signposting' would support the development of this narrative and ensure that the reader is on the intended journey. Signposting would include summarising the points that will be covered in each section, and linking between the different sections (showing how they relate to each other and in combination contribute towards the narrative). For example, having a more structured approach in the discussion of open science through outlining the broad themes that will be discussed.

The link to ethics is an interesting angle and one that could be made more explicit within the main body of the paper, rather than being mentioned in only the introduction and conclusion of the paper.

It feels like some of the points would benefit from additional references to support the points being made, as well as showing how this paper fits within current knowledge and practices.

At times, the authors introduce terms but don't really define them – for example, black-box models. Including short definitions of these terms, within the context of the paper, could help with reader comprehension and increase the impact of the points made.

To tighten the focus of the paper (on the ethics of open science in relation to energy) there is the opportunity to refine the literature discussed and focus on ideas that are of relevance to the overarching focus of the paper. For example, when discussing the prevention of bad research practices could this be linked back to energy or ethics in some way?

When listing multiple points, we feel the use of numbering would really improve the readability and clearly show the points that are being made. For example, when listing the functions of mainstream journals (page 4-5).

Introduction

Is there a way of mentioning ethics within this opening section?

Could additional references be included to provide the context/set up the need for this paper?

The stated aim of the paper is to analyse the adoption of open science and analyse its integration in the energy research domain – how is this being done i.e. through what methodology? Is it based upon a literature review or the researcher's experiences?

Open Science: Definition

When introducing the six principles of open science, signposting could be included in the paper along the lines of 'each of these principles will now be briefly introduced'.

At the end of the section, it would be useful to have a linking section of how this is relevant for the rest of the paper or link back to the idea of energy research.

Open science for prevention of bad research practices

Could the term 'bad research practices' be made more specific? This is slightly informal language at the moment.

This section could be set up in a clearer way – briefly summarising the main argument/s that are going to be discussed would be useful for the reader and would bring a flow to the paper.

The US Office of Research Integrity quote could perhaps be shortened.

The use of Feigenbaum and Levy's drawbacks of sharing scientific resources is a good way to set up the paragraph, perhaps an additional sentence saying 'these will now be discussed in more detail' would help readers, and a short discussion of the 'interference with future work'.

This section feels like a list of separate thoughts that are just put in a sequence one after the other, it would be nice if some of the points could be developed a bit further (and perhaps the number of points being made could be reduced to enable this and ensure you keep within the word count).

The mention of altmetrics is an interesting one, particularly as this provides a means for addressing the risk of bad research provided. It feels like greater detail could be provided on what is covered by altmetrics and why they themselves are not an 'incorrect' incentive.

Open science and energy research

We feel the word 'however' may not be needed before Pfenniger on page 5 as this suggests that this reference indicates that there are not positive outcomes, whereas the Pfenniger reference is actually highlighting four prevalent outcomes.

It would be nice to have an elaboration on how the homogenisation of metadata contributes towards the common understanding being established and in what way is data homogenised through open science.

We are not sure the relevance of the analogy related to optimisation tools – how does this relate to the overarching aim/narrative of the paper?

Perhaps an area to explore is why there may be variations between disciplines in terms of uploads to the Open Data Portal – what understandings, approaches, methods, schools of thought exist within these disciplines contributes to them uploading (or not uploading to the Open Data Portal).

It would be nice to more clearly set out the key messages that you're wanting to convey when presenting the different examples in this section, how do they come together and what do they say? Some sentences at the end of the paragraphs summarising responses to these questions would help guide the author through the section.

Discussion

The opening paragraph of this section is really effective and links directly to the aim outlined in the introduction. The points outlined in this paragraph could be better emphasised throughout

the main body of the text – these summary phrases could be used within the signposting.

As mentioned in the ‘General Points’ section of our review, there is the opportunity to have a more structured approach to the discussion of open science. A more structured approach may be facilitated by reducing the breadth of topics covered and go into greater detail on a few key points. In the current configuration, certain points could be expanded further, as the reader is left thinking ‘so what?’. These key points could then include greater reference to the ethics framing adopted within the paper.

Is the rationale for the Open Letter provided in sufficient detail? (Please consider whether existing challenges in the field are outlined clearly and whether the purpose of the letter is explained)

Partly

Does the article adequately reference differing views and opinions?

Partly

Are all factual statements correct, and are statements and arguments made adequately supported by citations?

Partly

Is the Open Letter written in accessible language? (Please consider whether all subject-specific terms, concepts and abbreviations are explained)

Partly

Where applicable, are recommendations and next steps explained clearly for others to follow? (Please consider whether others in the research community would be able to implement guidelines or recommendations and/or constructively engage in the debate)

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Energy-related Social Sciences and Humanities

We confirm that we have read this submission and believe that we have an appropriate level of expertise to state that we do not consider it to be of an acceptable scientific standard, for reasons outlined above.

Author Response 14 Jan 2025

Raquel Alonso Pedrero

Thanks for your comments, and sorry for our late response. We hope the new manuscript has a more straightforward message and that presents the discussion with a better narrative. General Comments:

This is an interesting paper which draws out and reflects open science within the context of energy research. Within the paper, focus is placed upon the ethical dimensions of open

science, although we feel this key message should be made more prominent in the paper's narrative before approval. **Response:**

Thank you for the feedback. We understand the concern about the key message, and we hope that you find the new manuscript much clearer and coherent. We addressed all of your comments below.

Comment 1:

Overall, the paper is well written but greater effort could be made to ensure the overarching narrative is clear and the central points are emphasised. The use of more 'signposting' would support the development of this narrative and ensure that the reader is on the intended journey. Signposting would include summarising the points that will be covered in each section, and linking between the different sections (showing how they relate to each other and in combination contribute towards the narrative). For example, having a more structured approach in the discussion of open science through outlining the broad themes that will be discussed.

Response:

We appreciate your feedback. We agreed that the old manuscript lacks a proper flow in the narrative which could make the reading challenging. We introduced signposting in all the sections of the new manuscript by i) initiating/finishing the sections and subsections with a reference to their following, ii) referring more often to concepts stated in previous sections to improve the coherence of the paper, iii) including bullet points and iv) incorporating subsections that connect with more broad themes. An example of this last point is the division of Section IV. Now, it is divided into A. Benefits of Open Science in Energy Research, B. Barriers and Limitations of Open Science in Energy Research and C. Integration of Open Science in Energy Research. These subsections are named the same as previous ones but with a focus on Energy Research. In this way, the new manuscript states a clear outline as suggested.

Comment 2:

The link to ethics is an interesting angle and one that could be made more explicit within the main body of the paper, rather than being mentioned in only the introduction and conclusion of the paper.

Response:

Thank you for appreciating the link to ethics. Based on the different reviewers and the rest of the paper, we decided to reduce the relevance of ethics and focus more on the integrity/application of open science. This is also stated by modifying the title from "Open science and ethics in energy research" to "Open science in energy research". However, we also believe that the link with ethics is still worth mentioning, so it is included in the introduction of the new manuscript.

Comment 3:

It feels like some of the points would benefit from additional references to support the points being made, as well as showing how this paper fits within current knowledge and practices. **Response:**

While the previous version of the article had 34 references, this number has increased to 45 in the current format. This accounts for the inclusion of important references suggested by the reviewers and new references added by the authors to support the points being made.

Comment 4:

At times, the authors introduce terms but don't really define them – for example, black-box models. Including short definitions of these terms, within the context of the paper, could

help with reader comprehension and increase the impact of the points made.

Response:

Thank you for pointing out the need for clearer words. We have addressed this by including a simple definition of black box models in a footnote to enhance reader comprehension. Additionally, we reviewed the manuscript and ensure that other technical terms were clarified to improve the accessibility of the paper.

Comment 4:

To tighten the focus of the paper (on the ethics of open science in relation to energy) there is the opportunity to refine the literature discussed and focus on ideas that are of relevance to the overarching focus of the paper. For example, when discussing the prevention of bad research practices could this be linked back to energy or ethics in some way?

Response:

We appreciate your feedback. Also, other reviewers noticed a lack of “connection” between parts of the paper. As such, the paper is structured such that the first part (Sections II and III) introduces open science in general, and the second part (Sections IV and V) dives into its impact, barriers and application in energy research. In the second part, the terminology from the first section is used regularly in the new manuscript to, as you suggested, discuss the links between ideas. We hope we have addressed this concern properly, as we believe it is key to the paper’s quality.

Comment 5:

When listing multiple points, we feel the use of numbering would really improve the readability and clearly show the points that are being made. For example, when listing the functions of mainstream journals (page 4-5).

Response:

We agree. As such, we integrated numbering and bullet points to make a clearer statement of lists or points. For instance, the key principles of open science in Section II are now presented in numbered bullet points, significantly improving readability and clarity.

Comment 6:

Introduction

- Is there a way of mentioning ethics within this opening section?
- Could additional references be included to provide the context/set up the need for this paper?
- The stated aim of the paper is to analyse the adoption of open science and analyse its integration in the energy research domain – how is this being done i.e. through what methodology? Is it based on a literature review or the researcher’s experiences?

Response:

- As mentioned in a previous response, the paper has been redefined not to be specific to ethics. Still, it is mentioned in Section I as a starting point for introducing open science as suggested.
- The paper includes new references to set up a better context and back up the ideas presented. However, we wanted to point out that as an open letter, we also include ideas from our own experience that may not have been so clearly stated in previous references.
- Thank you for pointing out the lack of clarity on implementation. The new manuscript dives more into this. We introduce the frameworks of FAIR and the Open Science Training Handbook and use them in the rest of the paper. Also, we introduce the

subsections: Applying open science (Section II) and Integration of Open Science in Energy Research to discuss how open science can be integrated and what is the current status of integration in energy research.

Comment 7:

Open Science: Definition

- When introducing the six principles of open science, signposting could be included in the paper along the lines of 'each of these principles will now be briefly introduced'.
- At the end of the section, it would be useful to have a linking section of how this is relevant for the rest of the paper or link back to the idea of energy research.

Response:

- The principles of open science are now presented in numbered bullet points.
- We appreciate this suggestion. We agreed that there is a lack of linkage between section II and energy research in the old manuscript. This also extends to section III. After considering the different options to tackle it, we believe that the more straightforward way to tackle this concern is to start Section IV as follows:

"Learning from the definitions, practices, benefits, and shortcomings of open science presented in the previous sections, the following focuses on the link these concepts to the particular domain of energy research."

Also, the entire text is linked by using the same terminology across sections. We hope these solutions, along with the structure change, help identify connections between ideas.

Comment 8:

Open science for prevention of bad research practices

- Could the term 'bad research practices' be made more specific? This is slightly informal language at the moment.
- This section could be set up in a clearer way – briefly summarising the main argument/s that are going to be discussed would be useful for the reader and would bring a flow to the paper.
- The US Office of Research Integrity quote could perhaps be shortened.
- The use of Feigenbaum and Levy's drawbacks of sharing scientific resources is a good way to set up the paragraph, perhaps an additional sentence saying 'these will now be discussed in more detail' would help readers, and a short discussion of the 'interference with future work'.
- This section feels like a list of separate thoughts that are just put in a sequence one after the other, it would be nice if some of the points could be developed a bit further (and perhaps the number of points being made could be reduced to enable this and ensure you keep within the word count).
- The mention of altmetrics is an interesting one, particularly as this provides a means for addressing the risk of bad research provided. It feels like greater detail could be provided on what is covered by altmetrics and why they themselves are not an 'incorrect' incentive.

Response:

- Fixed by referring to inappropriate practices
- The section is now divided into subsections, and each idea is briefly introduced in the title to facilitate identification of the arguments.

- As suggested, the definition was reduced as details were not discussed further.
- Thanks for noticing this issue in the readability. The discussion on issues for sharing scientific resources is now presented in two distinct subsections: 1) Additional Effort and Time Consumption and 2) Impact on Future Work and Competitiveness. This division facilitates the identification of the arguments and discussions.
- We hope the new structure and the rewritten discussions ease the reading flow.
- We thank the reviewer for the suggestion to deepen the understanding of Altmetrics. We expanded the explanation with an example, as we feel that a deeper dive into Altmetrics is beyond the scope of the text.

Comment 9:

Open science and energy research

- We feel the word 'however' may not be needed before Pfenniger on page 5 as this suggests that this reference indicates that there are not positive outcomes, whereas the Pfenniger reference is actually highlighting four prevalent outcomes.
- It would be nice to have an elaboration on how the homogenisation of metadata contributes towards the common understanding being established and in what way is data homogenised through open science.
- We are not sure the relevance of the analogy related to optimisation tools – how does this relate to the overarching aim/narrative of the paper?
- Perhaps an area to explore is why there may be variations between disciplines in terms of uploads to the Open Data Portal – what understandings, approaches, methods, schools of thought exist within these disciplines contributes to them uploading (or not uploading to the Open Data Portal).
- It would be nice to more clearly set out the key messages that you're wanting to convey when presenting the different examples in this section, how do they come together and what do they say? Some sentences at the end of the paragraphs summarising responses to these questions would help guide the author through the section.

Response:

- No longer applies
- Based on the research from Wierling et al., it has been shown that energy data and metadata are usually decentralized and not accessible to energy researchers, such that standards and nomenclature are not homogenised and standardised. Adopting centralised and open access platforms could enforce uniformity in how data and metadata are structured and shared and provide a common repository to eliminate double efforts.
- We have removed the analogy to optimisation in the effort to make the paper more general and accessible.
- Thank you for your suggestion. We also believe that this is an interesting area of research and as such it was mentioned in the discussion section.
- Thanks for your feedback. After revision, we also perceived a need for coherence and clarity. The entire section was rewritten with this in mind. The first noticeable change that could guide the reader better on the key messages is the division into three subsections. Each key idea is presented in a paragraph. For instance, in Section A, we start by linking it with the previous paragraph and introducing the benefits pointed out by Pfenniger. Each of these benefits is discussed in the following paragraphs.

Finally, the additional benefit of homogenisation of metadata is clearly stated and discussed.

Comment 10:

Discussion

- The opening paragraph of this section is really effective and links directly to the aim outlined in the introduction. The points outlined in this paragraph could be better emphasised throughout the main body of the text – these summary phrases could be used within the signposting.
- As mentioned in the ‘General Points’ section of our review, there is the opportunity to have a more structured approach to the discussion of open science. A more structured approach may be facilitated by reducing the breadth of topics covered and go into greater detail on a few key points. In the current configuration, certain points could be expanded further, as the reader is left thinking ‘so what?’. These key points could then include greater reference to the ethics framing adopted within the paper.

Response: Thank you for this suggestion. We believe that the current version of the discussion is improved due to important points flagged by the reviewers. Also, we restructured it such that we focused on the summarising the insights from the rest of the article and to showcase that open science has both advantages and barriers.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Report 14 July 2023

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.16970.r31995>

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Stephan Ferenz

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Thomas Wolgast

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General

The article gives an overview of the different aspects of Open Science and attempts to show the current state of Open Science in Energy Research.

The introduction nicely outlines the latest developments to Open Science and its relevance. It motivates why the state of Open Science in energy research is an important topic and relevant to analyze.

The second section introduces the concept of Open Science. While this introduction gives a good overview of six parts of Open Science (Open Access, Open Methodology, Open Data, Open Source, Open Review, Open Educational Resources) it would profit a lot when also introducing the concept

of FAIR (doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18¹) in respect to research data or research software (doi.org/10.3233/DS-190026²) and connecting it to Open Science. Also, this section is rather general and should be more specific.

The third section also addresses the general topic of Open Science and outlines how Open Science can improve research. While this is an important topic, its connection to energy research can be improved. Also, this section can be improved by reusing the categorization of the different aspects of Open Science from section II. Since Open Science in energy research is the main scope of the paper, we would recommend to shorten this section.

Finally, the fourth section analyzes Open Science in energy research. As in section III, this section can be improved by reusing the categorization of Open Science from section II. This section lists multiple examples that need to be connected more to a common theme. While most aspects have a connection to energy research, some are only vague connect, e.g. the Open Courseware in the last paragraph of the section. In some paragraphs of this section, the paper tries to differentiate between different areas of energy research (more industry related vs. more policy related) and their different levels and reasons for and against open science. This is an important aspect that should be analyzed with more effort and with more examples from the different areas of energy research. Furthermore, it should be discussed how the security aspect of research on the critical infrastructure plays a role here. Since this section is the main section of the paper, it would profit from dividing it into subsections. Also, this topic should be the longest part of the paper.

The last section of the paper discusses the different aspects of Open Science and outlines advantages and disadvantages. This part would profit from showing the connection of the different aspects to energy research.

We think the paper would also profit from an outlook section which could point out what additional research is needed to get a better overview of the state of Open Science in energy research.

Major Issues

1. In the context of open source, the term and concept of research software is important and should be integrated (e.g. doi.org/10.3233/DS-190026²).
2. The third paragraph in section IV focuses on metadata. Here, a link to existing approaches for metadata in the energy domain would be valuable (e.g. doi.org/10.3390/en14206692³).
3. The paper includes one figure. Unfortunately, the figure is not reproducible. The paper should reference to the actual dataset of the figure.
4. p6, "The number of entries for the energy category is remarkably low compared to other research fields": Well, it's a far more specialized field. This data is almost worthless without the number of publications or researchers in the respective fields for reference.
5. Publicly open conference are listed in the paragraph focusing on open educational resources. Scientific conferences are no educational resources. Also, it remains debatable if conference with conference fees can be counted as open.

6. The citation style with hyperlinks and without further information makes the links unusable if printed. Also, some examples (e.g. OpenMod) are also missing links. The missing links should be added and all links should also be marked in an additional way, e.g. footnotes.

Minor Issues

1. Section III has a subsection A but no subsection B. We would recommend to remove the subheading from this subsection.
2. The paper mainly uses the term energy research but sometimes also energy science. An uniform use of one term would improve the paper.
3. p4 "Allowing other researchers to reuse the data and methods [...] enhances the chance to detect bad research practices." -> Would the respective people use Open Science then? How does Open Science needs to be implemented to help with this problem?
4. p4/5, "barrier to implementing open access is related to the publishing industry revenue structure": Where exactly is the barrier here? The paragraph sounds like it's no problem at all.
5. p6: Is Energies a high-profile journal? MDPI is considered to be predatory by many researchers. (e.g. <https://academic.oup.com/rev/article/30/3/405/6348133>⁴)
6. p6, "Not pursuing openness...": This whole paragraph and the following one are difficult to understand.

References

1. Wilkinson MD, Dumontier M, Aalbersberg IJ, Appleton G, et al.: The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data*. 2016; **3**: 160018 [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
2. Lamprecht A, Garcia L, Kuzak M, Martinez C, et al.: Towards FAIR principles for research software. *Data Science*. 2020; **3** (1): 37-59 [Publisher Full Text](#)
3. Wierling A, Schwanitz V, Altinci S, Bałazińska M, et al.: FAIR Metadata Standards for Low Carbon Energy Research—A Review of Practices and How to Advance. *Energies*. 2021; **14** (20). [Publisher Full Text](#)
4. Oviedo-García M: Journal citation reports and the definition of a predatory journal: The case of the Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI). *Research Evaluation*. 2021; **30** (3): 405-419a [Publisher Full Text](#)

Is the rationale for the Open Letter provided in sufficient detail? (Please consider whether existing challenges in the field are outlined clearly and whether the purpose of the letter is explained)

Yes

Does the article adequately reference differing views and opinions?

Partly

Are all factual statements correct, and are statements and arguments made adequately

supported by citations?

Partly

Is the Open Letter written in accessible language? (Please consider whether all subject-specific terms, concepts and abbreviations are explained)

Yes

Where applicable, are recommendations and next steps explained clearly for others to follow? (Please consider whether others in the research community would be able to implement guidelines or recommendations and/or constructively engage in the debate)

No

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.**Reviewer Expertise:** Stephan Ferenz: Research data management and Open Science in Energy Research. Thomas Wolgast: Power Engineer interested in Open Science.**We confirm that we have read this submission and believe that we have an appropriate level of expertise to state that we do not consider it to be of an acceptable scientific standard, for reasons outlined above.**

Author Response 14 Jan 2025

Raquel Alonso Pedrero

Thanks for your valuable review and sorry for the late response. We hope this new manuscript and our responses tackle your comments appropriately.

General Comments: The article gives an overview of the different aspects of Open Science and attempts to show the current state of Open Science in Energy Research. The introduction nicely outlines the latest developments to Open Science and its relevance. It motivates why the state of Open Science in energy research is an important topic and relevant to analyze.

Response: Thank you for the detailed and meaningful feedback. It has definitely helped with the quality of the paper. We addressed each of the comments independently from each other below.

Comment 1: The second section introduces the concept of Open Science. While this introduction gives a good overview of six parts of Open Science (Open Access, Open Methodology, Open Data, Open Source, Open Review, Open Educational Resources) it would profit a lot when also introducing the concept of FAIR (doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.181) in respect to research data or research software (doi.org/10.3233/DS-1900262) and connecting it to Open Science. Also, this section is rather general and should be more specific. **Response:** Thank you for this suggestion. The FAIR concept is fundamental among researchers' practices nowadays (e.g., research proposals), thus the articles benefited from introducing it. The new manuscript includes subsection C. Applying open science (in Section II) where we included information from the two sources

suggested. Also, it was complemented by the introduction to The Open Science Training Handbook, which also provides a framework/guidelines for supporting researchers.

Comment 2: The third section also addresses the general topic of Open Science and outlines how Open Science can improve research. While this is an important topic, its connection to energy research can be improved.

Response: We appreciate your suggestion. We agree that the old manuscript did not link well enough the barriers and shortcomings of Open Science with energy research. As such, we explicitly mentioned the connection with the different barriers proposed by including subsection B. Barriers and limitations of Open Science in Energy Research in Section IV. We decided to keep Section III still open and general and specify the link with Energy Research in the following section.

Comment 3: Also, this section can be improved by reusing the categorization of the different aspects of Open Science from section II.

Response: Similarly to the response to Comment 2, Section III makes more explicit usage of the principles of Open Science.

Comment 4: Since Open Science in energy research is the main scope of the paper, we would recommend to shorten this section (referring to Section II).

Response: Thank you for the recommendation. Given some important points added (e.g., FAIR principles), and the feedback from the other reviewers, Section II was not shortened in the new manuscript. However, we understand the concern of the reviewer, so the section was rewritten to improve its flow and reduce redundant information. For example, we remove the link with the Mertonian values and focus on the specific definition of Open Science. Also, we include more signposting to support the narrative. We hope these modifications helps to address the reviewer's concern. We believe that, despite its length, this section introduces section IV (main scope).

Comment 5: Finally, the fourth section analyses Open Science in energy research. As in section III, this section can be improved by reusing the categorization of Open Science from section II.

Response: We agree. Therefore, the fourth section in the new manuscript elaborates in detail how the principles of Open Science tackle specific issues in energy research. The explicit mention of the principles is included throughout the entire section. Just to give an example, in the new manuscript we address the influence of lobbies and interest groups on quantitative research by emphasizing the principles of open methodology, open source, and open data:

"A notable example of mistrust stemming from a lack of transparent and accessible energy research is the concern that lobbies or interest groups could influence its results. In quantitative research, where the main tools used are mostly mathematical models, results are particularly sensitive to the data selection, allowing for potential pressure from interest groups to sway the interpretation and generation of results. To mitigate this mistrust, it is crucial to prioritise openness. This can be achieved by implementing open methodology (clear documentation of the methods), open source (providing access to the tools used), and open data (making data accessible). Such transparency is key to identifying assumptions, inaccuracies, and limitations in research and essential for recognising and addressing

potential pressures from interested parties.”

Comment 6: This section [Section IV] lists multiple examples that need to be connected more to a common theme. While most aspects have a connection to energy research, some are only vague connect, e.g. the Open Courseware in the last paragraph of the section.

Response: We thank the reviewer for the comment. We modified the section substantially to address this concern. In the new manuscript Section IV is divided into three subsections to be more direct on the topics discussed and how they relate to open science. Moreover, we added more detailed descriptions to clarify the connection to energy research in particular, even using our own experiences as examples.

Comment 7: In some paragraphs of this section, the paper tries to differentiate between different areas of energy research (more industry related vs. more policy related) and their different levels and reasons for and against open science. This is an important aspect that should be analyzed with more effort and with more examples from the different areas of energy research.

Response: We think you have a valid point. We have revised the section to better differentiate between industry and policy-related energy research. For instance, in the “Barriers and Limitations of Open Science in Energy Research”, we address the competitive and legal concerns in industry-driven research (e.g., proprietary models) versus policy-driven research that is often publicly funded. We also discuss, in section “Benefits of Open Science in Energy Research”, the heterogeneity between different areas of energy research and how centralized approaches of data sharing could enhance uniformity in how data and metadata are structured. We are confident that the new structure of the Section will clarify this concern by having a more coherent flow of ideas.

Comment 8: Furthermore, it should be discussed how the security aspect of research on the critical infrastructure plays a role here.

Response: We agree that this is an important topic of research and we appreciated this comment. We included the following paragraph in section IV addressing the trade-off between openness and security:

“Another area that faces challenges adhering to open science is research on critical infrastructure and cybersecurity. These fields are essential for securing key societal technologies, such as electricity and gas networks. As with the trade-off between innovation and restricted access to information, the risk of exposing sensitive security data and methods outweighs the benefits of making it public. In this case, the potential harm might be too great to justify complete openness.”

Comment 9: Since this section is the main section of the paper, it would profit from dividing it into subsections. Also, this topic should be the longest part of the paper.

Response: Thanks for the suggestion. The section is now divided into three subsections: A. Benefits of Open Science in Energy Research, B. Barriers and Limitations of Open Science in Energy Research and C. Integration of Open Science in Energy Research. These subsections were developed following the flow of the previous two sections. This suggestion helped to significantly improve the paper by stating a clearer connection with the rest of the paper (addressing previous comments). Also, we highlight the importance of the section by

expressing and signposting the goal of the section at the beginning of section IV.

Comment 10: The last section of the paper discusses the different aspects of Open Science and outlines advantages and disadvantages. This part would profit from showing the connection of the different aspects to energy research.

Response: We agree that the previous version lacked a proper link between energy research and open science. Following this recommendation, we decided to use Section IV to present more explicitly the aspects of open science and energy research.

Comment 11: We think the paper would also profit from an outlook section which could point out what additional research is needed to get a better overview of the state of Open Science in energy research.

Response: Thank you, we found this comment very meaningful to define better the scope of the paper. After the review we realized that the part discussing the state of Open Science in energy research aims to tackle a research question that requires a different approach from the one adopted in our paper. As such, answering this question outside the scope, so in order to avoid confusion, we remove the section comparing energy research with other disciplines. However, as it is an interesting research question worth mentioning, we have included it as further work in the Discussion section.

Issues Major Issues: 1. In the context of open source, the term and concept of research software is important and should be integrated (e.g. doi.org/10.3233/DS-1900262). We thank the reviewer for the valuable reference. We have included the definition in the manuscript. 2. The third paragraph in section IV focuses on metadata. Here, a link to existing approaches for metadata in the energy domain would be valuable (e.g. doi.org/10.3390/en142066923). Again, we thank the reviewer for the valuable reference. We have added information from the source in the manuscript. 3. The paper includes one figure. Unfortunately, the figure is not reproducible. The paper should reference to the actual dataset of the figure. 4. p6, "The number of entries for the energy category is remarkably low compared to other research fields": Well, it's a far more specialized field. This data is almost worthless without the number of publications or researchers in the respective fields for reference. In response to the reviewers' feedback in points 3 and 4, we have removed the figure and the analysis of the number of entries in the Horizon 2020 platform. As you correctly noted, a meaningful comparison would require a deeper analysis of the number of projects or researchers in each domain. 5. Publicly open conference are listed in the paragraph focusing on open educational resources. Scientific conferences are no educational resources. Also, it remains debatable if conference with conference fees can be counted as open. As pointed out, scientific conferences are not educational resources. The new manuscript does not include them. 6. The citation style with hyperlinks and without further information makes the links unusable if printed. Also, some examples (e.g. OpenMod) are also missing links. The missing links should be added and all links should also be marked in an additional way, e.g. footnotes. We understand this issue. The original draft included the full URLs in footnotes. Unfortunately, the editing process modified them to include hyperlinks. We will address this with the editors to consider the possibility of keeping the footnotes.

Minor Issues 1. Section III has a subsection A but no subsection B. We would recommend

to remove the subheading from this subsection. Solved with the change in structure 2. The paper mainly uses the term energy research but sometimes also energy science. An uniform use of one term would improve the paper. The change was made in the text, in favour of energy research. 3. p4 "Allowing other researchers to reuse the data and methods [...] enhances the chance to detect bad research practices." -> Would the respective people use Open Science then? How does Open Science needs to be implemented to help with this problem? This sentence is no longer part of the new manuscript. However, just to answer the questions, the idea of this argument is that reproducibility is encouraged. If so, "other researchers" can check whether the methods or the data correspond to the claims of the original authors. 4. p4/5, "barrier to implementing open access is related to the publishing industry revenue structure": Where exactly is the barrier here? The paragraph sounds like it's no problem at all. We thank the reviewer for this comment. A similar point was brought forward by another reviewer. The analysis of the decoupling argument in the first version of the paper was misdirected. The paragraph has been re-written to better convey the original message put up by the referenced papers. We hope to have made the motivation and the argument clearer. 5. p6: Is Energies a high-profile journal? MDPI is considered to be predatory by many researchers. (e.g. <https://academic.oup.com/rev/article/30/3/405/63481334>) This segment has been removed from the manuscript in the updated version. 6. p6, "Not pursuing openness...": This whole paragraph and the following one are difficult to understand. This paragraph has been rewritten.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.
